

1 **A polycomb switch involving loss of Ezh2 expression occurs during lymphocyte development.**

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6 We measured total transcription in the human hematopoietic stem cell (HSC) and in the major blood cell
7 types of the blood to discover genes required for blood cell specification. We discovered a recurrent
8 developmental pattern involving silencing or partial impairment of PRC2 through repression of *EZH2*
9 concomitant with HSC lineage specification and lineage restriction. In CD4+ T-cells, EZH2 silencing
10 occurred together with EZH1 induction, suggesting the existence of a polycomb switch that functioned
11 during HSC fate choice.

12 Citations

13 1. Ezhkova, E., Pasolli, H.A., Parker, J.S., Stokes, N., Su, I.H., Hannon, G., Tarakhovsky, A. and
14 Fuchs, E., 2009. Ezh2 orchestrates gene expression for the stepwise differentiation of tissue-specific stem
15 cells. *Cell*, 136(6), pp.1122-1135.